

UNRAVELLING LINKS BETWEEN FIBRE MISALIGNMENT, RESIN-RICH POCKETS, AND THE FIBRE BREAK DEVELOPMENT VIA *IN SITU* HOLOTOMOGRAPHY

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Keywords: CFRP, Synchrotron holo-tomography, Microstructural variations, Fibre breaks

ABSTRACT

Understanding the mechanical influence of microstructural variations on fibre break development is crucial for reducing uncertainties in predicting the longitudinal tensile failure of unidirectional composites. In this study, the interaction between local microstructural variations and fibre breaks is monitored using *in situ* X-ray holotomography at 150 nm resolution. Three distinctive microstructures are identified to drive the initiation and clustering of breaks. First, misplaced fibres within the 0°/0° interply region, which exhibit significant misorientation and cross multiple adjacent fibres, progressively trigger multiple single breaks and a co-planar cluster at their intersections. Second, resin-rich pockets within the 0°/0° interply region promote clustering of breaks, progressively forming a non-coplanar cluster of five breaks. This clustering is accompanied by non-uniform matrix microcracks and short interfacial debonds around the break sites. Third, larger resin-rich pockets, locally formed in regions with groups of misoriented fibres, play a critical role in driving pronounced break clustering. Their interactions exhibit severe matrix nonlinearity, as evidenced by matrix microcracks, short interfacial debonds, and damage features, including microvoids or the onset of matrix microcracks. The identified fibre break patterns, clustering behaviour, and damage associated with three microstructural cases provide new insights into how these microstructures serve as precursors to fibre break development, highlighting the importance of accounting for them in predicting longitudinal tensile failure to improve reliability.

1. Introduction

Carbon fibre-reinforced composites are now widely used in structural applications in the automotive, aerospace, and renewable energy sectors. Despite their widespread use, their relatively brittle structural response remains a key challenge in material design and failure prediction. Longitudinal tensile failure is arguably regarded as the most fundamental and crucial among all failure modes. It is widely recognised that the tensile final failure of multidirectional composites is determined by the failure of fibres oriented in the principal loading direction [1]. This failure scheme begins with the weakest fibres failing and culminates in the development of critical clusters that eventually trigger a self-sustaining cascade of fibre failures [2]. Each break diminishes load-carrying capacity, thereby redistributing the load to neighbouring fibres within a certain distance from the break. This redistribution is accompanied by shear-dominated deformation of both the matrix and the interface, involving various damage mechanisms such as matrix cracking and interfacial debonding.

To predict the size and severity of the region surrounding breaks, many studies have investigated stress redistribution around fibre breaks using finite element models [3-6]. However, uncertainties persist in these predictions, particularly because most models do not account for manufacturing-induced microstructural variations, such as severe local fibre misalignment and resin-rich pockets. In recent years, Synchrotron Radiation Computed Tomography (SRCT), pinnacle of computed tomography, has enabled 3D, *in situ*, imaging of composites at a resolution sufficient to distinguish individual fibre breaks [7, 8] and to correlate with microstructural features [9-11]. This has catalysed the opportunity for a deeper

understanding of how variations in microstructural features influence fibre breaks and, more broadly, composite strength in both experimental and numerical studies.

From an experimental perspective, Rosini *et al.* [11] examined the differences in local fibre misorientation between break and intact sites. Their statistical results demonstrated that fibres at single break sites have a higher standard deviation in their orientation distribution compared to intact fibre sites. Breite *et al.* [2] observed similar break behaviour through *in situ* SRCT, linking clustered breaks to fibre regions with significant in-plane misalignment. Findings from both studies remain limited to the initiation of single and clustered breaks, without elucidating the damage mechanisms that drive their formation and subsequent progression, or how clusters interact with local microstructural variations under increasing loads. In this context, Fritz *et al.* [12] used micro-CT to identify microstructural features in UD carbon fibre composites, but without performing *in situ* monitoring with applied loads. In particular, the study reported on the presence of *misplaced* fibres at ply interfaces, which deviate markedly from the main UD ply orientation and intersect multiple neighbouring fibres (as opposed to *misaligned* fibres, which may deviate from the nominal ply direction but are entirely constrained to their local tow).

FE models incorporating microstructural variations have also addressed their effects on stress localisation and composite strength. Malgioglio *et al.* [13] reported that increased variability in fibre misalignment reduced strength and increased the scatter in predicted strength values. Models in the study, however, are limited to the ply level. The replicated misorientation angles (-2° to 2°) remained insufficient to fully capture the range observed in commercially manufactured composites. Recently, Jafarypouria *et al.* [14] implemented microscale FE models to examine stress redistribution around a single fibre break in both misaligned and perfectly aligned fibres. This reported an increase of $\sim 33\%$ in the maximum stress concentration factors in neighbouring fibres for the misaligned case. However, the applicability of model is still limited by the studied range of misorientation angles (1.4° to 5°).

Although the studies discussed above have advanced the understanding of how local microstructural variations relate to tensile failure, two important questions remain open for further investigation:

- If fibres exhibit local misalignment exceeding the small angles typically studied ($<5^\circ$), similar to the misplaced fibres reported by Fritz *et al.* [12], how do severely misaligned fibres interact with adjacent aligned fibres, and how does this influence break behaviour under tensile loading?
- When fibres break at sites with local microstructural variations, how do the localised stresses interact with the surrounding matrix and fibre-matrix interfaces, and how might the resulting damage cause clustering of fibre breaks?

Whilst SRCT has been shown to be a valuable tool for understanding fibre failure, imaging at resolutions better than ~ 500 nm is rarely conducted due to constraints in image acquisition. Given this resolution level and scale of carbon fibres, isolated matrix microcracks and interfacial debonds may not be reliably detected, because their openings may be smaller than 30% of the voxel resolution. Even if such damage features exist, they can be obscured by bright fringes originating from discontinuities (i.e. fibre breaks), which are typically observed in propagation-based SRCT. To address these imaging limitations, Chatziathanasiou *et al.* [15] conducted the first *in situ* X-ray holo-tomography of composites at a 150 nm resolution. This technique, based on phase contrast nano-imaging, enabled the detection of matrix cracks and interfacial debonds initiated from breaks in glass and carbon fibre composites.

In this work, we extend the use of 150 nm *in situ* holo-tomography to elucidate interactions between local microstructural variations and fibre breaks under longitudinal tensile loading. Our primary objective was to link microstructural variations to the initiation and progression of breaks into clusters, along with associated microscale damage, such as matrix microcracks and interfacial debonds. In particular, we focus on three distinctive microstructures influencing fibre break development: (i) misplaced fibres, *i.e.* fibres crossing several other fibres, (ii) resin-rich pockets, and (iii) larger resin-rich pockets locally formed along groups of misoriented fibres. By addressing two key research questions outlined above, this study bridges a gap in understanding the influence of microstructural variations on longitudinal tensile failure.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

[90/0]_s cross-ply laminates of aerospace-grade carbon fibre/epoxy prepreg were provided by Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation, with a total thickness of ≈ 0.5 mm. MRZ65-18000 carbon fibre (Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation) was used, with a nominal fibre diameter of 5.4 μm and a tensile modulus of 287 GPa. A #350 series, amine curing epoxy (Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation) was used as the matrix and cured via a standard aerospace autoclave cycle in accordance with the manufacturer's specifications.

The epoxy matrix was doped with 2.3 vol.% of silicon dioxide particles (SiO_2 , 500 nm, near-spherical) to facilitate digital volume correlation on the tomograms. The selected particle properties were intended to minimise impact on the mechanical behaviour of the polymer matrix system, as suggested in [15, 16]. While digital volume correlation analysis was performed on these material/tests, the results are not a focus of this work and will not be discussed further.

2.2. Specimen design

Double-notched specimens, with a notch section width of 0.8 mm between the notch roots, were prepared for *in situ* tensile testing. The sample geometry is described in further detail in [15]. The volume fraction of 0° fibres in the notch region, as measured from the 3D reconstructed volume, was 48.5%. The specimens were machined using waterjet cutting, a method used previously for machining similar specimens without causing significant damage. Straight aluminium tabs, 1.5 mm thick, were attached to both faces and both ends of specimens using aerospace adhesive, Scotch-Weld™ EC-9323 B/A (3M Company, Maplewood, MN, USA), to aid loading and mitigate stress concentrations at the specimen ends.

Prior to the *in situ* experiments at ID16B beamline, *ex situ* tensile tests were performed on five specimens to determine the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) specific to the notch region. Given that the 0° plies were expected to primarily determine the longitudinal tensile failure of the specimens, only their cross-sectional area prior to the onset of 0° fibre splitting was used to calculate the UTS. The average of the measured UTS values was 2545 ± 168 MPa, serving as a reference for determining the stepwise loads applied during *in situ* testing.

2.3. *In situ* synchrotron holotomography

In situ holotomography scans were undertaken at 150 nm nominal (voxel) resolution on the ID16B beamline of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), Grenoble, France. Holotomography, based on phase contrast nano-imaging, delivers images with spatial resolutions down to 25 nm (voxel) and is particularly well suited to materials with low attenuation. For each scan at a given load level, four distinct holograms are acquired at different sample-to-detector distances, enabling the retrieval of detailed phase information. A single tomogram is therefore reconstructed with enhanced signal-to-noise ratio and improved image quality.

In situ tensile tests were performed using a screw-driven loading rig equipped with a 1 kN load cell, custom-designed at KU Leuven for integration with the beamline. A detailed description of the rig is provided in [15]. A tensile specimen was loaded to five incremental levels (5%, 67%, 86%, 91%, 96%) of the measured UTS, with scans taken at each level. A 2048×2048 pixel² detector (PCO Edge 4.2 CLHS sCMOS) was used, with geometrical magnification resulting in an effective voxel size of 150 nm. A “pink” beam with an energy of 29.6 keV was used [17]. Each scan acquired 2505 projections, with an exposure time of 10 ms per projection. Tomograms were reconstructed using in-house software at the ESRF [18].

3. Results and discussion

Fibre breaks formed in association with microstructural variations were identified in three regions (**Fig. 1**): misplaced fibres (Region 1), resin-rich pockets (Region 2), and larger resin-rich pockets locally formed along groups of misoriented fibres (Region 3). The causality of the breaks and their clustering was elucidated through hypothesised mechanisms contributing to the observed break behaviour, alongside microscale damage patterns developed near breaks.

Fig. 1. A 150 nm SRCT image of the tested specimen containing two 0° plies, acquired at 96% UTS, showing all fibre breaks within the scan volume projected as blue dots. The black rectangles at the $0^\circ/0^\circ$ interply ('Region 1' and 'Region 2') and 0° intraply ('Region 3') mark the cropping regions for the stacks containing break sites identified as interacting with microstructural variations. Each region shows the projection of identified breaks, with outlines colour-coded in green, yellow, and red, to indicate their formation at 86%, 91%, and 96%, respectively.

3.1. Misplaced fibres within the $0^\circ/0^\circ$ interply region

3.1.1 Fibre breaks linked to misplaced fibres

This is the first report of fibre break behaviour occurring in regions where misplaced fibres are present, as monitored by *in situ* scans. **Fig. 2a** illustrates the XZ plane view of the stack in Region 1 at 96% UTS, revealing three misplaced fibres (labelled as fibres 1, 2, and 3) in the interply region, with misorientation angles of -26° , 79° , and -35° , respectively. These angles represent the deviation of fibre orientations within the XZ plane relative to the Z-axis loading direction, with the positive direction defined as clockwise from the Z-axis.

The three misplaced fibres appear to cross and come into close contact with adjacent fibres. To investigate how these misplaced fibres relate to break occurrence, the stack was first projected along the Y-axis using the *average intensity* Z-projection in ImageJ. **Fig. 2b** presents the resulting XZ slice, highlighting the projections of nine break sites (1 to 9) spatially aligned with the misplaced fibres. In parallel, the XY cross-sectional views of the nine breaks were visually examined. As illustrated in **Fig. 3**, crossings between misplaced and adjacent fibres appear to progressively trigger seven single breaks and one co-planar break pair ('duplet') at load levels up to 96% UTS, either within the misplaced fibres or in the adjacent aligned fibres at their intersections.

Fig. 2. (a) XZ plane view of the stack cropped from Region 1 at 96% UTS, showing three misplaced fibres (labelled 1, 2, and 3) crossing adjacent fibres. (b) XZ slice obtained by average intensity projection of the Region 1 stack along the Y-axis, revealing nine break sites at intersections between misplaced and adjacent fibres.

Fig. 3. XY fibre cross-sectional views of nine breaks formed within the Region 1 stack (**Fig. 2b**), with all break sites located either within misplaced or adjacent fibres at intersections. Misplaced fibres 1 and 2 are labelled as M1 and M2, respectively. Each break number is colour-coded by formation load level, with centre coordinates defined relative to the XYZ axes of the Region 1 stack.

3.1.2 Role of misplaced fibres in break initiation

We propose two hypotheses to explain the mechanisms underlying the observed behaviour. First, the formation of multiple breaks at the intersections might be related to the tow spreading and resin impregnation process during prepreg manufacturing. These two processes, when carried out using the direct contact (mechanical) method, employ spreading or impregnation rollers to flatten the fibre tows into a uniform prepreg sheet, bringing the surface fibres on each ply into contact with the rollers during processing. This contact can build up shear and frictional stresses on the fibre tows, as indicated by Moradi *et al.* [19]. It is plausible that these stresses could concentrate on misplaced and misaligned fibre tows crossing over aligned fibres on the ply surface, potentially causing damage to the filaments within the fibre tows. This, in turn, could introduce strength controlling defects at the crossing points. Consequently, we hypothesise that such defects could explain the increased prevalence of fibre breaks within the interply region. Mesquita *et al.* [20] similarly reported a higher occurrence of fibre breaks

near the ply interface in thin plies, despite the absence of strongly misaligned fibres. This was suggested to result from the fibre weakening introduced during the tow spreading, which is consistent with the hypothesis we propose.

Another possible explanation for the observed breaks (1 to 9) involves micro-mechanical influences arising from local fibre misalignments, particularly local stress concentrations at intersections between misplaced and adjacent fibres. When fibre bundles were subjected to tension, misplaced fibres themselves may have experienced bending stresses in addition to axial stresses, placing them in a multiaxial stress state. This, in turn, may induce higher shear stresses in the matrix surrounding the misplaced fibres, leading to the formation of inhomogeneous stress states in nearby fibres. Crossing over adjacent fibres, misplaced fibres are likely to have intensified local stress concentrations at their intersections. Consequently, this could impart elevated stresses to misplaced or aligned fibres, or both, increasing their susceptibility to failure. Notably, **Fig. 3** illustrates co-planar breaks (4 and 5) formed at 86% UTS, when two misplaced fibres 1 and 2 crossed and contacted adjacent fibres. This phenomenon could be attributed to intensified local stress concentrations at intersections, exemplifying the micro-mechanical influences we proposed.

3.2. Resin-rich pockets within the 0°/0° interply region

3.2.1 Fibre break clustering and microscale damage linked to resin-rich pockets

A cluster in this study was defined as fibre breaks separated by less than 10 fibre diameters longitudinally (Z-axis) and two fibre diameters radially (X and Y-axis), consistent with the definition used in [8]. **Fig. 4** illustrates the primary findings of break clustering and associated microscale damage that progressively occurred along resin-rich pockets in Region 2 up to 96% UTS.

Fig. 4. (a) XZ plane view of the stack cropped from Region 2 at 96% UTS, showing non-coplanar breaks (1 to 5) near resin-rich pockets. Four marked positions (XY-1 to 4) indicate the locations used to extract XY cross-sectional planes at each break. (b) XY-1 and XY-2 planes of clustered breaks (1 to 3), revealing two distinct microscale damage patterns near resin-rich pockets, observed at 86%, 91%, and 96% UTS. The edges of matrix microcracks and fibres are delineated by orange and white dashed lines. (c) XY-3 and XY-4 planes at break 4, showing simultaneous formation of two microscale damage patterns.

No damage was observed in this region at 67% UTS. However, breaks 1 and 2 appeared as non-coplanar breaks at 86% UTS (**Fig. 4a**). The use of high-resolution phase contrast imaging facilitated a detailed examination of damage surrounding the breaks. The XY cross-sectional planes of each break reveal microscale damage in the form of matrix microcracks and short interfacial debonds (**Fig. 4b**). These two features contrast with their apparent absence around fibre breaks where no resin-rich pockets are present, as reported in [15]. Adjacent to break 1, a matrix microcrack of $\sim 1.1 \mu\text{m}$ in extent formed at break edges facing resin-rich pockets and extended into these regions, creating a non-uniform crack pattern around the fibre circumference (see XY-1 plane). The crack tips also appear distinctly wide/blunted as they extend into resin-rich pockets, resembling those observed near break 4 at 96% UTS (see YZ plane in **Fig. 4c**). In contrast, break 2 exhibited short interfacial debonds measuring $\sim 1.2 \mu\text{m}$ in axial length along the fibre direction (see XY-2 plane). These debonds were confined to the side opposite the resin-rich pockets, where the inter-fibre distance surrounding break 2 is small, leading to their asymmetric formation.

At 91% UTS, break 3 emerged in the vicinity of clustered breaks 1 and 2. While showing no visible debonds, the XY-1 break plane also reveals non-uniform matrix microcracks similar to those previously seen near break 1. With further loading to 96% UTS, additional breaks 4 and 5 formed in regions of fibres that were likely overloaded by neighbouring breaks 2 and 3. This consequently formed a non-coplanar cluster of five breaks (1 to 5) within approximately the same XZ plane located near resin-rich pockets. As shown in **Fig. 4c**, break 4 initiated matrix microcracking and short debonds simultaneously, consistent with the damage patterns seen near resin-rich pockets at lower loads (see XY-3 and XY-4 planes).

3.2.2 Role of resin-rich pockets in break clustering and microscale damage development

The observed patterns of matrix microcracks, characterised by non-uniform propagation towards resin-rich pockets with blunted crack tips, may be attributed to low local stiffness in resin-rich regions adjacent to broken fibre. These regions contain fewer surrounding fibres to suppress crack growth, permitting greater crack opening [5]. Despite their wide crack openings, the maximum extent of crack propagation remained relatively short ($\sim 1.6 \mu\text{m}$). This cracking behaviour could be indicative of shear nonlinearity locally occurring in the resin-rich regions. Yang *et al.* [21] suggest that shear nonlinearity in carbon epoxy composites may originate from microscale processes such as matrix microcracking. Molecular-level plasticity in the resin is also reported as a potential source of shear nonlinearity.

In contrast, the clustered breaks exhibited asymmetric debonding that was highly localised near break edges farther from resin-rich pockets, with debond lengths reaching no more than $\sim 1.5 \mu\text{m}$. This debonding can be explained by the localisation of shear stresses induced by breaks, which tend to concentrate more in regions with smaller inter-fibre distances rather than near resin-rich pockets. From an energy standpoint, the short extent of the debonds suggests that the strain energy released from a fibre break was not favourably absorbed through debonding. Rather, a greater portion of the energy was likely absorbed by matrix cracking and matrix plasticity, as discussed above.

In light of these findings, the continuous formation of matrix microcracks and short debonds from 86% UTS onwards indicates that resin-rich pockets may have played a significant role in promoting break clustering. This suggests that breaks near resin-rich pockets may induce more localised stress concentrations in the matrix and interface, thereby reducing effective matrix stiffness and introducing shear nonlinearity. As a result, neighbouring intact fibres near both newly formed and pre-existing breaks may become overloaded at each load level. This could increase the likelihood of cascading effects that promote the clustering of breaks under increasing loads, which may explain the formation of non-coplanar clusters within the interply region. Furthermore, another factor contributing to the clustering could be linked to the increased prevalence of breaks at or near the ply interface (see section 3.1.2).

3.3. Larger resin-rich pockets along misoriented fibre groups within the 0° intraply region

3.3.1 Fibre breaks linked to groups of misoriented fibres

Fig. 5 illustrates the primary findings on break initiation and clustering associated with groups of misoriented fibres and the resulting larger resin-rich pockets. The XY plane view of stack in Region 3

at 96% UTS is presented in **Fig. 5a**, showing projections of all breaks (1 to 22) formed at each load level within the stack. Groups of misoriented fibres are distributed across slices from XZ-1 to XZ-4 planes within the stack.

Fig. 5. (a) XY plane view of the stack cropped from Region 3, showing the projection of all detected breaks (1 to 22) within the stack, colour-coded by their formation load level. The black rectangle marks the cropping region containing the cluster sites. Five marked positions (XZ-1 to 4 and YZ-1) indicate locations used to extract XZ and YZ plane views at the cluster sites. (b) XZ plane view of ‘Y-stack I’ and an XZ slice obtained by average projection. (c) XZ plane view of ‘Y-stack II’ with magnified views of cluster sites at the XZ-3 and XZ-4 planes. Two marked positions (XY-1 to 2) indicate locations used to extract XY plane views at the cluster sites.

As shown in **Fig. 5b**, ‘Y-stack I’, sliced from XZ-1 to XZ-2 planes, is found to contain the most severely misoriented group of fibres, which collectively cross over adjacent aligned fibres with misorientation angles of 8° . Accordingly, larger resin-rich pockets were formed along the regions occupied by these misoriented fibres. The breaks accumulated up to 96% UTS in the Y-stack I are effectively visualised in 2D using the average projection along the Y-direction, consistent with the method used in section 3.1.1. Breaks consistently occurred at intersections between misoriented fibre groups and adjacent fibres, closely resembling the break behaviour observed near misplaced fibres (see section 3.1.1). As such, we propose that micro-mechanical effects, i.e. local stress concentrations arising at the intersections, could be linked to this break behaviour, consistent with the hypothesis proposed on breaks linked to misplaced fibres. In addition, Jafarypouria *et al.* [14] demonstrated that peak stress concentration factors in the neighbouring intact fibres near a break were $\sim 33\%$ higher in misaligned fibre bundles than in perfectly aligned ones, which further supports our hypothesis.

3.3.2 Fibre break clustering and microscale damage linked to larger resin-rich pockets

Fig. 5c presents ‘Y-stack II’, sliced from XZ-3 to XZ-4 planes within the Region 3 stack. A labelled region, referred to as cluster sites, contains non-coplanar breaks that developed near larger resin-rich pockets locally formed along misoriented fibre groups. Most of these breaks predominantly developed within the same XZ break planes up to 96% UTS, as revealed by 2D slices taken at XZ-3 and XZ-4 planes.

At 86% UTS, two pairs of non-coplanar breaks emerged: breaks 6 and 7 in the XZ-3 plane, and breaks 1 and 2 in the XZ-4 plane. In the XZ-3 plane, larger resin-rich pockets are clearly visible around the site of breaks 6 and 7, resulting from misoriented fibre groups. These misoriented fibres were also in contact with those identified in Y-stack I. As part of the clusters, breaks 7 and 1 lay within the same XY-2 fibre cross-sectional break plane and were located immediately adjacent to each other, forming a co-planar duplet. This co-planar duplet initiated both matrix microcracks and short interfacial debonds, showing damage patterns consistent with those observed around breaks located near resin-rich pockets (see section 3.2.1).

At 91% UTS, three additional breaks were detected in close proximity to the non-coplanar breaks formed in the XZ-3 and XZ-4 planes: a single break 8 and non-coplanar duplet (9 and 3). The focus of observation was on breaks 9 and 3 because their break sites were immediately adjacent to the pre-existing co-planar duplet (7 and 1) and non-coplanar breaks (1 and 2). **Fig. 6a** additionally shows the breaks (9 and 3) in the YZ-1 plane view of the cluster sites. The lower left side of break 3 in the YZ-1 plane shows damage features, appearing as microvoids or the onset of matrix microcracks, within the inter-fibre matrix region between breaks 9 and 3, facing the larger resin-rich pockets. Similarly, damage features resembling microvoids were observed on the upper left side of break 3 in the XZ-4 plane (**Fig. 6a**), particularly within inter-fibre matrix region between break 2 and 3. These features were absent in the scans at lower loads, indicating that their formation is related to the surrounding break behaviour.

Fig. 6. (a) XZ and YZ plane views of the cluster sites (**Fig. 5c**) in ‘Y-stack II’ at XZ-4 and YZ-1 planes, showing non-coplanar breaks with associated microscale damage at 86%, 91%, and 96% UTS. Break numbers are colour-coded by their formation load level. (b) XY fibre cross-sectional views of non-coplanar breaks at 96% UTS, taken from cluster sites at XY-1 and XY-2 planes. Matrix microcracks near break 3 propagate extensively (black arrows), linking breaks 1, 3, 7, and 9, which formed earlier at 86% and 91% UTS.

At 96% UTS, two single breaks 4 and 13 were newly detected in fibres facing larger resin-rich pockets, with break 4 forming immediately next to the pre-existing non-coplanar cluster (1 to 3) in the XZ-4 plane. This progressive clustering also formed new microvoids within the inter-fibre matrix region between breaks 4 and 3, as observed at 91% UTS. As the pre-existing non-coplanar breaks (1 to 4) and (3 and 9) opened further with increasing load, the surrounding earlier-formed damage features (i.e. onset

of matrix microcracks) increased in size. As seen in YZ-1 plane (**Fig. 6a**), the damage features within the inter-fibre region of breaks 3 and 9 eventually coalesced, linking these two breaks that were previously unlinked at earlier loads. This damage progression, evident as significant propagation of matrix microcracks, was similarly observed along the inter-fibre regions of the pre-existing clustered breaks (7 and 9) and (7 and 1). **Fig. 6b** illustrates the XY-1 and XY-2 planes of these breaks at 96% UTS, revealing matrix microcracks at their maximum propagation in the fibre cross-sectional view. In the XY-1 plane, matrix microcracks initiated at break 3 prominently propagate across the inter-fibre matrix region toward the fibre where break 9 occurred, located near the larger resin-rich pockets. Consequently, the propagating matrix microcracks appear to connect with those surrounding clustered breaks 9, 7, and 1, forming a continuous damage zone.

Together with the micro-mechanical effects discussed earlier, we tentatively propose a hypothesis that could explain the pronounced increase in clusters near larger resin-rich pockets in Y-stack II. Following the formation of initial breaks near resin-rich pockets, stress redistribution between broken and neighbouring intact fibres may have been hindered by the combined effects of fibre misalignment, larger resin-rich pockets, and matrix nonlinearity. Moreover, the observed clustering was consistently accompanied by the formation of by matrix microcracks, short interfacial debonds, and microvoids. These damage features provide evidence of severe matrix nonlinearity in these break sites. Notably, with increasing loads, the propagation of matrix microcracks extended across the inter-fibre region, progressively linking pre-existing clustered breaks. This exemplifies the severity of matrix nonlinearity, particularly when break sites are influenced by both fibre misalignment and the resulting resin-rich pockets. Furthermore, Swolfs *et al.* [4] reported that the tips of matrix cracks may induce very high stress gradients across fibres. If so, these gradients could play an additional role in intensifying matrix nonlinearity, further supporting our hypothesis.

4. Conclusions

This study investigates the interaction between local microstructural variations and fibre breaks in 0° carbon fibre plies, elucidating how these interactions contribute to the initiation and clustering of breaks. We performed *in situ* tensile tests, combined with 150 nm-based X-ray synchrotron holo-tomography, to monitor the accumulation of breaks in regions with microstructural variations under increasing stress levels. The scans revealed three distinctive microstructural features that promote a pronounced increase in the occurrence of single and clustered breaks: misplaced fibres and resin-rich pockets within the 0°/0° interply region, and larger resin-rich pockets surrounding misoriented fibre groups within the 0° intraply region. Notably, the clustering of breaks near resin-rich pockets was consistently accompanied by non-uniform matrix microcracks, short interfacial debonds, and damage features resembling microvoids or onset of matrix microcracks. Such microscale damage strongly suggests the occurrence of severe matrix nonlinearity at these break sites, reinforcing the role of resin-rich pockets in promoting break clustering. The identified break patterns and associated microscale damage shed new light on the importance of considering their critical role in fibre break development for more reliable predictions of longitudinal tensile failure. Future work could focus on developing fibre break models that incorporate the microstructural variations identified in this study. This would help determine the extent to which these microstructural variations influence stress redistribution around breaks.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the contributions from the Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation (Advanced Molding and Composites Laboratory, Aichi R&D centre, Japan) and the dedicated MCC scientists – Fukuhara Yasuhiro, Takano Tsuneo, Sugiura Naoki – for their sponsorship, material supplies, and technical support. We also acknowledge the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) for the provision of synchrotron radiation facilities at the ID16B beamline under proposal number MA5729, and we greatly appreciate the technical support of Julie Villanova and Olga Stamati. We extend deepest gratitude to our colleagues – Babak Fazlali and Sina AhmadvashAghbash – for their invaluable assistance and insightful advice during the synchrotron experiments. The μ -VIS X-Ray Imaging Centre at the University of Southampton is acknowledged for providing image post-processing tools. Lastly, we acknowledge the KU Leuven Research Council for project C14/21/076 and the Research Foundation

Flanders for the postdoctoral fellowships ToughImage (126342IN), BIOPTOUGH (12B0624N), and COCOMI (1231322N).

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